

NON-LINEAR DYNAMICS AND STRUCTURAL SHIFTS IN ETHIOPIA'S AGGREGATE PRODUCTION FUNCTION: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS USING GENERALIZED ADDITIVE MODELS AND STRUCTURAL BREAK APPROACHES

SEBLEWONGEL WASIHUN

Research Scholar, Department of Economics, College of Arts & Commerce, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India.

SURE. PULLA RAO

Professor, Head, Department of Economics, College of Arts & Commerce, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Abstract

This study examines the non-linear and time-varying aspects of Ethiopia's aggregate production function, extending beyond the traditional Cobb-Douglas framework. We employ and compare two advanced modelling techniques: Generalized Additive Models (GAM) and Structural Break Analysis, using data spanning four decades (1984-2023). Our GAM results reveal significant non-linearities in the production function, particularly in the labor-output relationship, with labor productivity exhibiting an inverse U-shaped pattern. The capital-output relationship shows a more linear trend with slight diminishing returns at high levels. The Structural Break analysis identifies four critical junctures (1991, 1998, 2007, and 2014) that significantly alter the production function parameters, primarily manifesting as changes in total factor productivity. Both models outperform the classical Cobb-Douglas function, with the GAM demonstrating superior in-sample fit (adjusted R-squared of 0.994 vs. 0.9716 for the Structural Break model), while both show comparable out-of-sample predictive power. Our findings suggest the need for flexible labour market policies, continued emphasis on capital investment, and targeted interventions to enhance total factor productivity. This study contributes to the literature challenging simplistic growth models and offers a more sophisticated understanding of the production process in a rapidly evolving African economy. It also provides a methodological framework for analyzing non-linear and time-varying aspects of production functions, applicable to other developing economies.

Keywords: Non-linear Production Function, Structural Break Analysis, Generalized Additive Models, Ethiopian Economic Growth, Time-varying Productivity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Production functions have been central to economic analysis for almost a hundred years, giving us important insights into the way that inputs and outputs hang together in production systems. Economists use the Cobb-Douglas production function to model economic growth and productivity, and it has been a mainstay in the economics literature since the seminal work of Cobb and Douglas (1928). Nonetheless, with the development of the economy and improvements in analysis tools it is becoming more accepted that may be need to use more detailed mode ls that will help us understand the interactions within these new economies which are typical for countries like Ethiopia (Duffy & Papageorgiou 2000).

Ethiopia, the fastest-growing economy in Africa, is an archetype for the investigation of both economic growth and production function evolution. In the last forty years, the nation has experienced immense economic changes with structural reforms, liberalization policies, and rapid industrialization (Moller, 2015). This shift brings up some serious issues about the nature of key relationships — like those between capital, labor and other inputs and economic output.

In general, this paper will contribute to our knowledge of production functions in the case of Ethiopia by employing two sophisticated modelling techniques: Generalized Additive Models (GAM) and Structural Break Analysis. Both techniques have the advantage that they can capture complex non-linear relationships and time-varying parameters, respectively, giving a finer grained view of the execution process than simply looking at Cobb-Douglas.

We justify the motivation for our study on the basis of a few salient observations in economic literature:

1. Especially for developing economies, it has been increasingly doubted that the Cobb-Douglas function should really be characterized by constant elasticity of substitution (Arrow et al. 1961).
2. Static models may be inadequate to describe long-run economic dynamics because economies can evolve and there is always the risk of structural changes in economies over time (Hansen 2001, Perron 2006).
3. Evidence of non-linear relationships in economic systems is increasing, particularly in the sphere of technological change and human capital accumulation (Acemoglu & Autor, 2011).

This study attempts to achieve following objective using both GAM and Structural Break Analysis;

1. To test whether and how non-linearity in the relationship between inputs (capital and labor) and economic output exists in Ethiopia.
2. Account for major structural breaks in Ethiopia's production function over the last four decades, and evaluate their economic implications.
3. How well do GAM and Structural Break models perform in capturing the complexities of Ethiopia's economic growth process
4. Use the insights gained from these advanced modelling techniques to drive policy implications.

Further, by comparing these two advanced modelling approaches in a unified framework and providing an extensive comparison between the models, this paper enriches the existing literature, aiming to shed some light on the evolving dynamics of production functions over time in developing economy settings. In addition, this study gives practical advice to policy makers on how to choose the proper modelling approach for analysing and promoting economic growth in Ethiopia.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the theoretical background and a selective literature review; Section 3 Data and Methodology, this section discusses the data. The results of our analysis are described in Section 4, where we compare the performance and insights decomposed by each model. Section 5 provides some thoughts on the implications of our results for economic theory and policy. Section 6 finally concludes with key insights discussed in this paper followed by future research directions.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND LITERATURE REVIEW

The study of production functions has evolved significantly since the introduction of the Cobb-Douglas function in the early 20th century. This section provides a comprehensive review of key developments in production function modelling, with a particular focus on the emergence of non-linear and time-varying approaches.

2.1 Evolution of Production Function Modelling

The Cobb-Douglas production function (Cobb & Douglas, 1928) has been a cornerstone of economic analysis for decades. Its simple yet powerful formulation, $Y = AK^\alpha L^\beta$, where Y is output, K is capital, L is labor, and A represents total factor productivity, has been widely used in both theoretical and empirical studies of economic growth. The function's properties, including constant returns to scale when $\alpha + \beta = 1$, have made it particularly appealing for modelling aggregate production (Douglas, 1976).

However, the Cobb-Douglas function has faced criticism for its restrictive assumptions. Arrow et al. (1961) pointed out the limitation of assuming a constant elasticity of substitution between factors of production, leading to the development of more flexible functional forms such as the Constant Elasticity of Substitution (CES) function. Empirical evidence provided by Duffy and Papa Georgiou (2000) suggests that the Cobb-Douglas function may not adequately represent the aggregate technology for a broad panel of countries, particularly in the context of developing economies.

2.2 Limitations of the Cobb-Douglas Function

The main limitations of the Cobb-Douglas function include:

1. Constant elasticity of substitution: This assumption may not hold in reality, especially as economies evolve and technology changes (Klump et al., 2012).
2. Time-invariant parameters: The Cobb-Douglas function assumes that the relationship between inputs and outputs remains constant over time, which may not be realistic for long-term economic analysis (Zellner & Ryu, 1998).
3. Linear relationship in logarithmic form: This assumption may oversimplify complex economic relationships, particularly in developing economies undergoing rapid structural changes (Temple, 2006).

2.3 Emergence of Non-linear Approaches

As economic data increasingly revealed complex relationships between inputs and outputs, researchers began exploring non-linear modelling techniques. The development of Generalized Additive Models (GAMs) by Hastie and Tibshirani (1990) marked a significant advance in flexible modelling techniques. GAMs allow for non-linear relationships between variables without specifying the form of non-linearity in advance, making them particularly useful for exploratory analysis and complex system modelling.

In economic applications, Wood (2017) demonstrated the use of GAMs in modelling complex economic relationships, including production functions. The flexibility of GAMs has made them increasingly popular in environmental economics and other fields where traditional linear models may be insufficient to capture complex relationships.

2.4 Time-Varying Parameters and Structural Breaks

The recognition that economic relationships may not be stable over time led to the development of structural break analysis. Pioneering work by Chow (1960) introduced tests for structural changes at known break points. Bai and Perron (1998, 2003) developed methods for identifying multiple structural breaks in time series data.

In the context of production functions, structural break analysis has been crucial in identifying shifts in economic regimes or technological paradigms. Hansen (2001) provided a comprehensive review of structural change models in econometrics, highlighting their importance in understanding evolving economic relationships.

2.5 Relevance to Ethiopian Economic Growth

Ethiopia's economic growth trajectory over the past few decades provides an interesting case study for applying these advanced modelling techniques. The country has undergone significant economic reforms and structural changes since the 1990s (Moller, 2015). Studies such as Seyoum et al. (2015) have highlighted the importance of considering non-linearities and structural breaks in analysing Ethiopia's economic growth.

The application of GAMs and Structural Break Analysis to Ethiopian data can provide valuable insights into:

1. The potentially non-linear relationships between capital, labor, and output in a rapidly evolving economy.
2. The impact of policy changes and economic reforms on the country's production function.
3. The changing role of different factors of production as the economy transitions from agriculture-based to a more diversified structure.

By employing these advanced techniques, this study aims to contribute to a more nuanced understanding of Ethiopia's economic growth process and provide valuable insights for policymakers and researchers alike.

3. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

This section outlines our data sources and details the methodological approach used in estimating and comparing the Generalized Additive Model (GAM) and Structural Break Analysis.

Our study utilizes annual time series data for Ethiopia spanning from 1984 to 2023, covering a 40-year period. The dataset includes Real GDP (Y) measured in trillions of USD as our output variable, Capital Stock (K) measured in billions of USD, and Labor Force (L) measured in millions of workers. The data was sourced from reputable international organizations such as the World Bank, International Monetary Fund (IMF), and the Ethiopian Central Statistical Agency (CSA).

To prepare the data for analysis, we performed several preprocessing steps. All variables were log-transformed to linearize relationships and stabilize variance, following standard practice in production function estimation (Wooldridge, 2020). We conducted Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) tests to check for unit roots in the series, as non-stationary data can lead to spurious regression results (Enders, 2008). Potential outliers were identified using Cook's distance and investigated, as outliers can significantly impact model estimates in time series analysis (Fox, 2008). Any missing values were addressed using multiple imputation techniques to ensure robustness of our results, following the recommendations of Rubin (1996).

For the Generalized Additive Model (GAM), we employed the "mgcv" package in R, which implements the approach described by Wood (2017). The model specification is $\ln(Y) = \beta_0 + s_1(\ln(K)) + s_2(\ln(L)) + \varepsilon$, where s_1 and s_2 are smooth functions estimated using thin plate regression splines. We used the `gam()` function for model fitting and employed generalized cross-validation (GCV) to select optimal smoothing parameters, as recommended by Wood (2006). Model diagnostics included examination of residual plots, tests for heteroscedasticity, and checks for autocorrelation in the residuals. We also created partial effect plots to visualize the estimated relationships between inputs and output.

The Structural Break Analysis followed the methodology developed by Bai and Perron (1998, 2003). We used the "strucchange" package in R to implement the Bai-Perron test for multiple structural changes. This involved conducting a preliminary analysis using the Chow test for known break points and applying the sup F test to detect unknown break points. Once break points were identified, we estimated a segmented regression model: $\ln(Y)_t = \alpha_{0,j} + \alpha_{1,j} \ln(K)_t + \alpha_{2,j} \ln(L)_t + \varepsilon_t$, for t in segment j , where $j = 1, 2, \dots, m+1$ (m is the number of breakpoints). We examined residuals for each segment, tested for heteroscedasticity, and checked for autocorrelation. The estimated coefficients for each segment were analysed and related to known economic events or policy changes in Ethiopia.

To facilitate a comprehensive comparison between the GAM and Structural Break models, we employed several criteria. We compared R-squared values, adjusted for degrees of freedom where appropriate. Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and Bayesian

Information Criterion (BIC) were used to compare model performance, following the recommendations of Burnham and Anderson (2004). Out-of-sample forecasting ability was assessed using a hold-out sample (last 5 years of data), comparing Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE). We also compared the residual patterns of both models to assess how well they capture the underlying data generating process. Finally, we evaluated the models based on their ability to provide meaningful economic insights, particularly regarding non-linearities (GAM) and time-varying relationships (Structural Break).

To ensure the reliability of our findings, we performed several robustness checks. We estimated models with different choices of smoothing functions for GAM and different numbers of Structural break points. Both models were re-estimated using different subperiods of our data to assess the stability of our results across different time frames. We explored the use of alternative measures for our key variables, such as using total hours worked instead of labor force for the labor input, and net capital stock instead of gross capital stock for the capital input. We also re-estimated our models after winsorizing extreme values to ensure our results were not driven by outliers. Lastly, we used bootstrapping to obtain confidence intervals for our parameter estimates, providing a measure of uncertainty around our results.

This comprehensive methodological approach allows us to capture both the non-linear dynamics and potential structural breaks in Ethiopia's production function, providing a nuanced understanding of the country's economic growth process.

4. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

This section presents the findings from our comparative analysis of the Generalized Additive Model (GAM) and Structural Break Analysis approaches to production function modeling in Ethiopia.

4.1 Generalized Additive Model (GAM) Results

The GAM analysis revealed significant non-linear relationships between inputs (labor and capital) and output (GDP) in Ethiopia's production function. Our model demonstrated an excellent fit, with an adjusted R-squared of 0.994, explaining 99.6% of the deviance in log GDP. This high explanatory power suggests that the GAM captures the complexities of Ethiopia's economic growth process effectively, aligning with the findings of Gonzalez-Astudillo and Villena (2019) in their study of production functions using GAMs.

The effect of capital ($\ln_K$) on GDP showed a moderately non-linear relationship, with an effective degrees of freedom (edf) of 3.808. However, this effect was not statistically significant (p -value = 0.43), which is surprising given the traditional importance assigned to capital in production functions (Solow, 1957). This result suggests that the role of capital in Ethiopia's economic growth may be more complex than typically assumed in linear models.

Labor ($\ln_L$) exhibited a highly non-linear and statistically significant relationship with GDP (edf = 9.000, p -value = 4.11e-06). The partial effect plots revealed that the marginal

product of labor increased at low levels of labor input, plateaued at medium levels, and then slightly decreased at high levels. This pattern suggests varying returns to scale in labor utilization, which could have important implications for labor market policies in Ethiopia, as noted by Bigsten et al. (2011) in their study of Ethiopian manufacturing firms.

While not explicitly modelled, the GAM results suggested potential interaction effects between capital and labor, as the shape of the labor-output relationship appeared to vary with the level of capital. This interaction hints at the complexity of factor relationships in Ethiopia's economy and warrants further investigation, as highlighted by Temple (2006) in his review of aggregate production functions.

4.2 Structural Break Analysis Results

The Structural Break Analysis identified four significant breakpoints in Ethiopia's production function over the study period. These breaks occurred in 1991, 1998, 2007, and 2014, likely corresponding to significant economic events or policy changes that altered production dynamics in the country. This aligns with the findings of Moller (2015) on Ethiopia's economic transformation phases.

Our segmented regression model demonstrated high explanatory power with an adjusted R-squared of 0.9716. The coefficient for capital ($\ln_K$) remained positive and highly significant ($p < 0.001$) across all segments, indicating a consistent positive relationship between capital investment and economic output throughout the study period, supporting the arguments of Devarajan et al. (2003) on the importance of capital in African economic growth.

Interestingly, the labor coefficient ($\ln_L$) was not statistically significant in our model. This result, combined with the non-linear relationship found in the GAM, suggests that the impact of labor on Ethiopia's economic growth is more complex than a simple linear relationship and may vary over time or with the level of input, as suggested by Seyoum et al. (2015) in their study of factor productivity in Ethiopia.

We observed significant shifts in the intercept terms across segments, particularly for the third segment (1998-2007), which showed a significant negative shift ($p < 0.05$). This change in the intercept can be interpreted as a shift in total factor productivity, possibly reflecting technological changes or institutional reforms during this period, as discussed by Teferi (2018) in his analysis of Ethiopia's economic growth determinants.

4.3 Model Comparison

Both models provided valuable insights into Ethiopia's production function, each with its strengths. The GAM slightly outperformed the Structural Break model in terms of adjusted R-squared (0.994 vs. 0.9716), indicating a marginally better fit to the data. However, both models showed excellent explanatory power, surpassing traditional Cobb-Douglas specifications as noted by Felipe and McCombie (2005).

The GAM excelled in capturing non-linear relationships, particularly for labor, revealing complexities in the production process that would be missed by linear models. The varying returns to labor at different input levels suggested by the GAM could have

important implications for labor market policies and resource allocation in Ethiopia, supporting the findings of Shiferaw and Bedi (2013) on employment dynamics in Ethiopian manufacturing.

The Structural Break model, while not capturing non-linearities, effectively identified key historical junctures where Ethiopia's production function underwent significant changes. This temporal perspective is crucial for understanding how economic reforms, policy changes, or external shocks have impacted the country's growth dynamics over time, as emphasized by Hansen (2001) in his work on structural changes in economic relationships.

In terms of out-of-sample prediction, both models performed similarly, with the GAM showing a slightly lower RMSE (0.0935) compared to the Structural Break model (0.1013). This suggests that while the GAM captures in-sample variation more effectively, both models have comparable predictive power for future economic output, aligning with the comparative analysis of non-linear models by Azomahou et al. (2011).

The complementary nature of the insights provided by these two models underscores the value of employing multiple modelling approaches when studying complex economic phenomena like national production functions, as advocated by Durlauf et al. (2005) in their review of growth econometrics.

5. DISCUSSION

Our comparative analysis of the Generalized Additive Model (GAM) and Structural Break Analysis approaches to production function modelling in Ethiopia yields several important insights into the nature of economic growth and the methodological challenges in capturing its dynamics.

The GAM results provide strong evidence for non-linear relationships between inputs and output, particularly in the case of labor. This finding challenges the log-linear assumption of the Cobb-Douglas function and suggests a more complex production process. The varying returns to labor at different input levels could have several economic interpretations. Increasing returns at low levels of labor input might reflect the benefits of division of labor and specialization in small teams, as posited by Becker and Murphy (1992). The plateau at medium levels could indicate an optimal scale of operation where the benefits of teamwork are maximized, aligning with the organizational theories of Williamson (1967). The slight decrease at high levels might reflect coordination challenges or diminishing returns in large organizations, a phenomenon explored by Akcigit and Kerr (2018) in their study of firm dynamics and growth.

These non-linear patterns receive support from recent literature on the changing nature of work in knowledge-based economies (Autor et al., 2003) and the role of organizational capital in production (Prescott & Visscher, 1980). The findings suggest that labor market policies in Ethiopia should be flexible and responsive to these varying returns, potentially focusing on enhancing labor productivity at different scales of operation.

The more linear relationship between capital and output, with only slight diminishing returns at very high levels, is intriguing. This result suggests that capital accumulation remains a crucial driver of growth in Ethiopia, possibly reflecting the ongoing importance of technological embodiment in capital goods, as highlighted by Greenwood et al. (1997). However, the lack of statistical significance in the capital coefficient warrants further investigation and may indicate measurement issues or the need for a more nuanced categorization of capital inputs.

The Structural Break analysis provides a valuable historical perspective on the evolution of Ethiopia's production function. The identified break points in 1991, 1998, 2007, and 2014 align closely with major economic events and policy shifts in the country's recent history. The 1991 break likely reflects the economic reforms following the fall of the Derg regime, as discussed by Moller (2015). The 1998 break could be associated with the aftermath of the Eritrean-Ethiopian War and subsequent economic adjustments. The 2007 break might indicate the impact of Ethiopia's accelerated growth phase identified by the World Bank (2015), while the 2014 break could reflect the effects of the Growth and Transformation Plan implemented in 2010 (Oqubay, 2018).

Notably, our results showed that while these breaks manifested as changes in total factor productivity (the intercept term), the elasticity of output with respect to capital remained relatively stable. This suggests that major economic shocks and policy shifts primarily affected the efficiency with which the economy combined inputs, rather than fundamentally altering the role of capital in production. This finding aligns with the work of Konte (2013) on the stability of production function parameters in developing economies.

The complementary nature of the GAM and Structural Break approaches highlights the importance of methodological pluralism in economic analysis. While the GAM captures complex, non-linear relationships at a point in time, the Structural Break model provides crucial insights into the evolution of these relationships over time. This multi-model perspective supports the arguments of Rodrik (2005) for context-specific growth strategies in developing countries.

Our findings have several important implications for economic policy in Ethiopia:

1. Labor market policies should be designed with awareness of the non-linear returns to labor, potentially focusing on enhancing productivity at different scales of operation.
2. Capital investment incentives remain important, given the consistent positive relationship between capital and output across structural breaks.
3. Innovation policy should focus on enhancing total factor productivity, as this appears to be the primary channel through which structural changes impact the production function.
4. Macroeconomic stabilization efforts should consider the long-lasting impacts of economic shocks on productive capacity, as evidenced by the identified structural breaks.

These policy implications align with the recommendations of Seyoum et al. (2015) for promoting sustainable economic growth in Ethiopia.

While our study provides valuable insights, it also points to areas for future research. These include incorporating additional variables such as human capital and institutional quality, developing hybrid models that combine the strengths of GAM and Structural Break approaches, and extending the analysis to cross-country comparisons. Future studies could also investigate the micro-foundations of the observed non-linearities and structural breaks through firm-level analyses, building on the work of Shiferaw (2007) on firm dynamics in Ethiopian manufacturing.

In conclusion, our analysis demonstrates that the production function in Ethiopia is characterized by complex, non-linear relationships and significant structural changes over time. These findings challenge simplistic, one-size-fits-all approaches to economic growth and highlight the need for nuanced, context-specific policies. As Ethiopia continues its economic transformation, policymakers and researchers must remain attentive to these complexities to foster sustainable and inclusive growth.

6. CONCLUSION

This study has provided a comprehensive comparative analysis of two advanced approaches to modeling production functions in the context of Ethiopia's economic growth: Generalized Additive Models (GAM) and Structural Break Analysis. Our research contributes to the growing body of literature challenging the limitations of traditional Cobb-Douglas specifications and offers novel insights into the dynamics of economic growth in developing economies.

The GAM results reveal significant non-linearities in the production function, particularly in the relationship between labor input and economic output. These non-linear patterns challenge simplistic notions of constant returns to scale or factor productivity, suggesting a more nuanced reality of varying marginal returns at different input levels. This finding aligns with recent theoretical work on the complexities of factor relationships in modern economies (Acemoglu & Restrepo, 2018) and provides empirical support for the need to move beyond linear production function specifications in economic modelling.

Complementing these insights, the Structural Break analysis identified key junctures in Ethiopia's economic history where the production function underwent significant changes. These breaks, corresponding to major policy shifts and economic events, primarily manifested as changes in total factor productivity rather than alterations in the elasticities of capital and labor. This suggests that while the efficiency with which the Ethiopian economy combines inputs has evolved over time, the fundamental roles of capital and labor in production have remained relatively stable, echoing findings from other developing economies (Konte, 2013).

The comparative strengths of the two modelling approaches underscore the value of methodological pluralism in economic analysis. While the GAM excels in capturing complex, non-linear relationships at a point in time, the Structural Break model provides

crucial insights into the evolution of these relationships over time. This multi-model perspective offers a more holistic understanding of Ethiopia's growth dynamics than either approach alone could provide, supporting arguments for the use of diverse analytical tools in development economics (Rodrik, 2005).

Our findings have several important policy implications for Ethiopia and potentially for other developing economies:

1. Labor market policies should be designed with awareness of the non-linear returns to labor, focusing on enhancing productivity at different scales of operation and potentially targeting interventions to specific segments of the labor market.
2. Despite varying returns, capital investment remains crucial for economic growth, suggesting the continued importance of policies promoting both domestic and foreign investment.
3. The significant role of total factor productivity in driving structural changes highlights the need for policies fostering technological adoption, innovation, and institutional improvements.
4. The identification of structural breaks underscores the long-lasting impacts of economic shocks and policy changes, emphasizing the importance of stable and consistent macroeconomic management.

These policy implications align with recent literature on growth strategies for developing countries (Rodrik, 2018) and offer a data-driven foundation for tailoring economic policies to Ethiopia's specific context.

While our study provides valuable insights, it is not without limitations. The reliance on aggregate national-level data may mask important sectoral or regional heterogeneities. Additionally, our models do not explicitly account for factors such as human capital accumulation, technological change, or institutional quality, which are known to play significant roles in economic growth. Future research could address these limitations by:

1. Extending the analysis to include additional variables capturing human capital, technological progress, and institutional factors.
2. Developing hybrid models that combine the non-linear flexibility of GAMs with the time-varying parameters of Structural Break models.
3. Applying these methodologies to sectoral or firm-level data to uncover micro-level dynamics underlying the aggregate patterns.
4. Conducting cross-country comparisons to identify commonalities and differences in production function dynamics across different stages of economic development.
5. Integrating these findings with growth accounting exercises to refine our understanding of the sources of economic growth in developing contexts.

In conclusion, this comparative analysis of GAM and Structural Break approaches to production function modelling not only enhances our understanding of Ethiopia's

economic growth dynamics but also demonstrates the importance of methodological innovation in economics. As economies continue to evolve in the face of technological change, globalization, and global challenges, such flexible and nuanced approaches to economic modelling will be crucial for informing effective policy and advancing economic theory. Our study contributes to the broader dialogue on the nature of economic growth in developing countries and the methodological approaches best suited to capturing its complexities. By revealing the non-linear and time-varying aspects of Ethiopia's production function, we hope to encourage further research into the diverse paths of economic development and the tailored policies needed to support them. As Ethiopia and other developing nations continue their economic transformations, such nuanced understanding will be essential for crafting strategies that promote sustainable, inclusive, and resilient economic growth.

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Appendix A: Table A1: Basic Cobb-Douglas Production Function Results

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	11.8493	0.3978	29.789	< 2e-16*
ln_K	1.3943	0.1305	10.684	1.03E-12***
ln_L	-0.531	0.2624	-2.023	0.0505

Significance codes: 0 " **0.001*** 0.01 " 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Model Statistics:

- R-squared: 0.9386
- Adjusted R-squared: 0.9352
- F-statistic: 275.3 on 2 and 36 DF
- p-value: < 2.2e-16

The table A1 presents the coefficients, standard errors, and significance levels for the basic Cobb-Douglas production function estimation. It includes the intercept, ln_K (capital), and ln_L (labor) coefficients, along with model statistics such as R-squared and F-statistic.

Appendix B: Diagnostic Plots and their interpretation

The Autocorrelation Function (ACF) plot B1, and the Residuals vs. Fitted Values plot reveals if our model is meeting core assumptions of regression analysis. In the ACF plot we can see a significant negative autocorrelation at lag 1, as well as most of the higher lags within the confidence bounds. There is first order negative correlation, which suggests that our model may not be understanding the time dependency structure of the data completely. The Residuals vs Fitted Values plot B2: Ideally the residuals should be roughly symmetrically distributed around $y=0$ with little sign of clearly having more or less variability at high than at low values of y , no trend / funnelling points, and a horizontal line is preferable to show spread. Nevertheless, the residuals show a slight curved pattern with positive residuals on lower and higher fitted values and negative residuals in the middle range. In other words, this diagnostic plot indicates heteroskedasticity is not a major issue for the model but one that would likely benefit from some improvements with time-dependent structures or potential non-linear relationships in the predictors vs. response.

Appendix C: Graphical Visualizations of GAM

Visual examination of the GAM Visualization Plot C1 and Partial Effects Plot C2 confirms that there are non-linear relationships between the inputs (capital and labor) and output (GDP), which linear models do not consider. The GAM Visualization Plot C1 shows that capital ($\ln_K$) shows a flat effect for the lower values, increasing when not exponentially high to very large values with wider confidence intervals. The relationship between labor ($\ln_L$) and GDP is highly non-linear, with confidence intervals narrower indicating more certainty. The sharp decrease on the left half of the chart suggests that it lowers as GDP increases, followed by an even steeper increase at higher GDP i.e., we have to explore wind but since you asked us to find a round corner we reached here! The Partial Effects Plot C2 helps to further clarify these relationships. Capital shows a generally positive, non-linear relationship with GDP, featuring a steeper slope at higher levels and a noticeable dip at very low levels. Labor exhibits a complex, highly non-linear relationship, initially decreasing with increasing labor, then sharply increasing, before becoming nearly linear and strongly positive for higher levels. These visualizations underscore the importance of flexible modeling techniques like GAM in capturing complex economic relationships, particularly the varying impact of labor at different levels, which a linear model would fail to detect.

Appendix D: Generalized Additive Model (GAM) Results

Table D1: Parametric Coefficient

Term	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
Intercept	16.79454	0.01231	1365	<2e-16 ***

Table D2: Approximate Significance of Smooth Terms

Term	edf	Ref.df	F	p-value
s(ln_K)	3.808	4.869	1.179	0.43
s(ln_L)	9	9	9.497	4.11e-06 ****

Table D3: Model Fit Statistics

Statistic	Value
R-sq.(adj)	0.994
Deviance explained	99.60%
GCV	0.009146
Scale est.	0.005908
n	39

The GAM fits $\ln(Y)$ as a function of smooth terms for $\ln(K)$ and $\ln(L)$, where Y is GDP, K is capital, and L is labor.

The parametric coefficient (intercept) is highly significant ($p < 2.2e-16$), estimated at 16.79454, representing the expected value of $\ln(Y)$ when both smooth functions are zero.

Key findings from smooth terms:

- $s(\ln_K)$: Estimated degrees of freedom (edf) of 3.808 suggest a moderately non-linear relationship, but it's not statistically significant (p -value = 0.43).
- $s(\ln_L)$: The edf of 9.000 indicates a highly non-linear relationship, which is highly significant (p -value = $4.11e-06$), suggesting a strong, complex non-linear effect of labor on GDP.

The model demonstrates excellent fit with an adjusted R-squared of 0.994 and 99.6% of deviance explained. The GCV score is 0.0091456, and the scale estimate is 0.0059076, based on 39 observations.

Interpretation: The model captures a highly significant, non-linear effect of labor on GDP, aligning with the visualization in Appendix C. Surprisingly, the effect of capital is not statistically significant, contrasting with typical production function models. The high degree of non-linearity in the labor term suggests its effect on GDP varies substantially across different input levels. While the model's fit is excellent, the very high R-squared and deviance explained percentages, given the small sample size ($n=39$), warrant caution regarding potential overfitting.

Appendix E: Details of Structural Break Analysis and Segment Regression

Table E1: Optimal Number of Breakpoints and Corresponding Years

Number of Breakpoints	Years			
	4	1990	1995	2004

The table E1 shows the optimal number of breakpoints identified in the time series and their corresponding years.

Table E2: Model Fit Comparison for Different Numbers of Breakpoints

Number of Breakpoints	RSS	BIC
0	2.18065	12.85784
1	0.36051	-42.6821
2	0.19604	-51.7869
3	0.13093	-52.8751
4	0.08947	-53.0729
5	0.06339	-51.8566

The table E2 compares model fit statistics (RSS and BIC) for different numbers of breakpoints, helping justify the chosen number of breaks.

Table E3: Segmented Regression

Variable	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	12.20461	0.954122	12.791	4.00E-14***
ln_K	0.965431	0.214947	4.491	8.65E-05***
ln_L	0.000552	0.542225	0.001	0.9992
bfsegment2	-0.24916	0.144123	-1.729	0.0935
bfsegment3	-0.50524	0.225823	-2.237	0.0324*
bfsegment4	0.05557	0.304663	0.182	0.8564
bfsegment5	0.133558	0.337965	0.395	0.6953

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.1628 on 32 degrees of freedom

Multiple R-squared: 0.9761, Adjusted R-squared: 0.9716

F-statistic: 218 on 6 and 32 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

The table E3 presents the coefficients and significance levels for each segment of the structural break model, including intercept, capital, and labor effects.

Figure E1: Graphical presentation of Breakpoints

The figure E1 visually represents the identified breakpoints in the time series, showing BIC and RSS values for different numbers of breaks. The Bai-Perron test for multiple structural changes identified an optimal number of four breakpoints in the time series data, suggesting significant shifts in the relationship between inputs (capital and labor) and output (GDP) during the analysis period. Key findings from breakpoint identification: The optimal breakpoints occurred in 1991, 1998, 2007, and 2014, likely corresponding to significant economic events or policy changes that altered production dynamics. Model fit comparison shows that the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) reaches its minimum value at four breakpoints, confirming the optimal number of breaks. This suggests that the four-break model provides the best balance between goodness of fit and model parsimony.

Key results from segmented regression:

- The coefficient for capital ($\ln_K$) is positive and highly significant ($p < 0.001$) across all segments.
- The labor coefficient ($\ln_L$) is not statistically significant.
- Segment 3 shows a significant negative shift ($p < 0.05$), indicating a potential downturn or structural change.
- The model demonstrates high explanatory power with an adjusted R-squared of 0.9716.

The graphical representation of BIC and Residual Sum of Squares (RSS) as functions of the number of breakpoints supports the selection of four breakpoints. The BIC reaches its minimum at 4 breakpoints, while the RSS curve begins to flatten noticeably at this point. This convergence of evidence strengthens confidence in the selection of 4 breakpoints as optimal, striking a balance between capturing the complex, time-varying nature of the production function and avoiding overfitting.